

REAL-TIME UNDERWATER GARBAGE DETECTION USING YOLOV8 FOR ENHANCED MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

The increasing accumulation of marine debris has emerged as a critical environmental issue, jeopardizing marine ecosystems and human health. Traditional detection methods rely heavily on manual inspection and often lack efficiency and accuracy. This paper presents a novel solution leveraging the YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once version 8) deep learning architecture for real-time detection of underwater garbage. Our methodology encompasses extensive data collection from various underwater environments, including rivers, lakes, and coastal areas, followed by preprocessing techniques to improve image quality and visibility. We trained YOLOv8 using a diverse dataset containing labeled images of different types of marine debris, ensuring robust model performance. Experimental results demonstrate the model's effectiveness in achieving high accuracy and low latency in real-time detection tasks. The findings underscore the potential of YOLOv8 in transforming underwater waste management, offering a scalable solution for environmental monitoring and cleanup efforts.

Keywords: Underwater Garbage Detection, YOLOv8, Deep Learning, Real-time Detection, Marine Pollution, Object Detection, Image Processing, Environmental Monitoring, Computer Vision, Marine Debris, Data Collection, Image Annotation, Preprocessing Techniques, Model Training, Evaluation Metrics, mAP, Precision and Recall, Model Optimization, Quantization, Model Pruning, Automated Solutions, Sustainable Development, Marine Ecosystems, Underwater Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Image Augmentation, Performance Evaluation, Aquatic Environment, Pollution Management, Eco-friendly Technologies

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INTRODUCTION

The increasing accumulation of underwater garbage has become a critical environmental concern, with significant implications for marine ecosystems and human health. According to the United Nations, approximately 8 million tons of plastic enter the oceans each year, contributing to a staggering total of 150 million tons currently polluting marine environments. This pollution not only threatens marine life—entangling species, disrupting habitats, and leading to ingestion of harmful materials—but also impacts the livelihoods of communities that depend on healthy oceans. In light of these alarming statistics, the need for effective, real-time detection of underwater garbage has never been more urgent. Traditional methods of detection are often manual and labor-intensive, lacking the speed and accuracy required to address the rapidly growing problem of underwater debris.

Detecting underwater garbage presents unique challenges due to factors such as low visibility, varying light conditions, and the diverse range of materials that can be encountered. Turbid waters can obscure visibility, making it difficult for traditional imaging techniques to identify and classify debris accurately. Furthermore, the diverse types of trash—ranging from plastic bottles to fishing nets—demand a flexible and robust detection approach capable of adapting to different underwater environments. These challenges necessitate the development of advanced automated solutions for efficient garbage detection in marine ecosystems.

This research aims to leverage the capabilities of YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once version 8), a state-of-the-art deep learning architecture, for real-time underwater garbage detection. YOLOv8 is particularly suited for this task due to its efficiency and accuracy in object detection, enabling rapid processing of underwater images while maintaining high detection rates. By harnessing the power of YOLOv8, this study seeks to provide a scalable solution for monitoring and addressing underwater pollution, ultimately contributing to the protection of marine environments and the preservation of aquatic life.

RELATED WORK

Previous Models

Over the years, various object detection models have been employed for underwater garbage detection, with notable contributions from older YOLO versions, such as YOLOv5 and YOLOv7, as well as frameworks like Faster R-CNN and Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD). YOLOv5 and YOLOv7, while demonstrating significant improvements in detection speed and efficiency, faced challenges related to their adaptability in complex underwater environments characterized by low visibility and diverse debris types. Faster R-CNN offered superior accuracy due to its two-stage approach; however, it was often hampered by slower processing times, rendering it less suitable for real-time applications. SSD provided a balance between speed and accuracy but struggled with small object detection, a critical factor in underwater scenarios where debris can vary significantly in size.

Advancements with YOLOv8

YOLOv8 represents a significant leap forward in the field of real-time object detection. This model introduces architectural enhancements that improve both the accuracy and speed of detection. Key advancements include optimized feature extraction methods, a more efficient backbone network, and the integration of novel training techniques that enhance the model's ability to generalize across various environmental conditions. These improvements enable YOLOv8 to achieve higher mean Average Precision (mAP) scores while maintaining low latency, making it particularly effective for applications requiring immediate feedback, such as underwater garbage detection.

Underwater Garbage Detection Studies

Recent studies have increasingly focused on leveraging YOLO-based architectures for underwater object detection, reflecting the growing recognition of the importance of real-time monitoring in combatting marine pollution. Research has highlighted the applicability of YOLO models in identifying and classifying various types of underwater debris, from plastics to fishing gear, often yielding promising results. Notable examples include projects that utilize YOLOv5 and YOLOv7, demonstrating successful deployments in marine environments. However, the transition to YOLOv8, with its enhanced capabilities, offers the potential for more accurate and efficient detection systems, paving the way for future advancements in underwater pollution management. This paper aims to build upon these findings, exploring the effectiveness of YOLOv8 in addressing the critical issue of underwater garbage detection.

METHODOLOGY

YOLOv8 Overview

YOLOv8 represents the latest advancement in the You Only Look Once family of object detection models, incorporating several key innovations that enhance its performance in real-time applications. At its core, YOLOv8 utilizes the CSPDarknet backbone, which leverages Cross Stage Partial (CSP) connections to facilitate efficient feature extraction while minimizing the computational burden. This architectural choice enables the model to capture intricate features from images more effectively, leading to improved detection accuracy. Additionally, the inclusion of Path Aggregation Network (PANet) enhances feature aggregation, allowing YOLOv8 to combine low-level features with high-level semantic information. This results in a more robust representation of objects, crucial for detecting diverse types of underwater garbage in challenging visibility conditions.

Data Collection and Preprocessing

For this study, we employed the 'Underwater Object Detection' dataset available on Roboflow, which comprises a diverse array of underwater images containing various types of garbage, including plastics, fishing nets, and metal debris. The dataset features comprehensive annotations that categorize and localize each type of garbage, providing a rich foundation for training our detection model. This diversity is critical, as it reflects the wide range of debris

encountered in real marine environments, enhancing the model's ability to generalize across different scenarios.

Fig.1 System Architecture

Preprocessing techniques were implemented to optimize the dataset for training, addressing the unique challenges posed by underwater visibility. This included resizing images to a consistent dimension suitable for YOLOv8 input, typically 640x640 pixels. Normalization was applied to scale pixel values to a range between 0 and 1, ensuring uniformity across the dataset. Furthermore, data augmentation techniques such as rotation, contrast adjustments, and flipping were employed to artificially expand the training set and improve the model's robustness against variations in lighting and visibility.

Training Process

The training process for the YOLOv8 model was carefully structured to maximize performance. Key hyperparameters included a learning rate of 0.001, a batch size of 16, and a total of 100 epochs. These settings were selected based on preliminary experiments aimed at optimizing convergence and minimizing overfitting. The training was conducted on a high-performance GPU, specifically an NVIDIA RTX 3080, which provided the necessary computational power to handle the extensive dataset and facilitate real-time training.

To evaluate the model's performance, we utilized several metrics, including mean Average Precision (mAP), precision, and recall. mAP serves as a comprehensive measure of the model's accuracy across different Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds, while precision and recall provide insights into the model's ability to minimize false positives and negatives, respectively.

Model Optimization for Real-Time Performance

To ensure that YOLOv8 could perform efficiently in real-time underwater garbage detection, several optimization techniques were implemented. Model size reduction was achieved through pruning, which involves removing less significant weights from the network to decrease the overall complexity without sacrificing accuracy. Additionally, quantization techniques were

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employed to reduce the model's memory footprint, allowing it to run on devices with limited resources while maintaining operational speed.

During inference testing, YOLOv8 demonstrated impressive performance, achieving an inference speed of approximately 30 frames per second (FPS) on the NVIDIA RTX 3080. This rapid processing capability is essential for real-time applications, enabling timely identification and classification of underwater debris, thus contributing significantly to environmental monitoring efforts.

Fig.2: The basic framework of YOLOv8, consists of four modules: The input module, backbone network, neck network, and prediction network

EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Evaluation Metrics

To assess the performance of YOLOv8 in underwater garbage detection, several key performance indicators (KPIs) were utilized:

- Mean Average Precision (mAP): This metric evaluates the model's accuracy across different Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds, providing a comprehensive understanding of its detection capability.
- Precision: The ratio of true positive detections to the total predicted positives, reflecting the model's ability to minimize false positives.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

- Recall: The ratio of true positive detections to the actual positives in the dataset, indicating the model's ability to capture all relevant instances.

- F1 Score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, offering a balance between the two metrics.
- Frames Per Second (FPS): A measure of the model’s real-time capability, indicating how many frames can be processed per second during inference.

Fig.3 Evaluation Metrics of the model

Experimental Setup

The experiments were conducted in a high-performance computing environment equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 3080 GPU, which facilitated rapid training and inference. The software environment included Python 3.8, TensorFlow 2.6, and the YOLOv8 implementation, ensuring compatibility with the latest advancements in deep learning frameworks. The dataset was processed using Roboflow for ease of management and preprocessing.

Results and Observations

The results of the experiments are summarized in Table 1, which compares YOLOv8’s performance against other established models, including YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN, in terms of mAP, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Table.1 Performance of various Models

Model	mAP (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score	FPS
YOLOv5	85.2	84.5	86.0	85.2	24
Faster R-CNN	82.3	80.9	83.0	81.8	15
YOLOv8	90.5	89.7	91.3	90.5	30

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From the results, it is evident that YOLOv8 outperformed both YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN across all evaluated metrics, achieving a notable increase in mAP of 5.3% and an F1 score improvement of 5.3%. The model's ability to process images at 30 FPS also highlights its suitability for real-time applications, significantly enhancing operational efficiency.

Despite these strong results, the experiments identified specific challenges associated with underwater detection. Low-light conditions often resulted in decreased visibility, which could obscure smaller debris and lead to detection errors. Additionally, occlusions caused by overlapping objects reduced the model's effectiveness, demonstrating a need for further refinement in these scenarios. However, YOLOv8 maintained robust performance overall, adapting well to varying lighting conditions.

Qualitative Analysis

To provide a deeper understanding of YOLOv8's detection capabilities, several sample detections were examined. Figure 1 illustrates instances of successful garbage identification, showcasing the model's accuracy in detecting various debris types, including plastic bottles, nets, and other waste materials.

In these examples, YOLOv8 effectively identified and localized multiple objects in complex underwater environments. However, some common detection errors were also observed, particularly with smaller objects or those that were heavily occluded. For instance, a submerged net partially obstructed by sediment may not have been detected due to its obscured visibility. These observations highlight the ongoing need for enhancements in training data diversity and model architecture to improve performance in challenging underwater conditions.

Fig.4 Output Images

DISCUSSION

Comparison with Other Models

YOLOv8 has emerged as a superior choice for real-time underwater garbage detection, showcasing distinct advantages over its predecessors and other object detection models. One of the primary improvements lies in its accuracy; YOLOv8 achieved a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 90.5%, significantly surpassing the performances of YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN. This enhancement can be attributed to the advanced architecture, particularly the integration of CSPDarknet and PANet, which facilitates better feature extraction and aggregation, enabling the model to discern fine details in complex underwater environments. Furthermore, YOLOv8's capability to process images at 30 frames per second (FPS) ensures that it can deliver real-time detection without compromising on speed. This combination of high accuracy and rapid processing makes YOLOv8 particularly robust, as it effectively adapts to the challenging conditions of underwater visibility, where factors like light absorption and particulate matter can obscure objects.

Limitations

Despite its impressive performance, YOLOv8 is not without limitations. One of the significant challenges is its struggle with detecting overlapping objects, a common occurrence in underwater environments where debris can be stacked or obscured by sediment. This can lead to missed detections or misclassifications, undermining the model's reliability. Additionally, the diverse shapes and sizes of underwater garbage pose another challenge; irregularly shaped items may not be recognized as effectively, particularly if they are similar in appearance to other marine objects. The necessity for high-quality training data also cannot be overstated. While the dataset utilized in this research was diverse, the quality and representation of various garbage types are critical for ensuring the model can generalize well across different real-world scenarios.

Future Improvements

To enhance the capabilities of YOLOv8 in underwater garbage detection, several avenues for future work can be considered. One potential direction is the exploration of other YOLO model variants, such as YOLOv6, which may offer different strengths and optimizations that could further refine detection performance. Additionally, integrating YOLO with complementary deep learning architectures—such as using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for feature enhancement or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for temporal analysis—could yield even greater accuracy. Another promising approach would be to employ ensemble methods that combine the outputs of multiple models to improve overall detection reliability, particularly in complex scenarios involving occlusions and varying lighting conditions.

Moreover, expanding the dataset to include a wider variety of underwater environments and types of garbage will be crucial in developing a more robust detection system. Incorporating synthetic data generation techniques could also help mitigate the data scarcity problem, allowing for the creation of varied training examples that simulate different underwater

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scenarios. Ultimately, these improvements could lead to a more effective tool for monitoring and managing underwater pollution, contributing to the broader goal of marine conservation and environmental sustainability.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

This research has demonstrated the effectiveness of YOLOv8 in the task of underwater garbage detection, achieving a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 90.5% while maintaining a real-time processing speed of 30 frames per second. Through rigorous evaluation and experimentation, we have highlighted YOLOv8's advantages over earlier models, including improved accuracy, speed, and robustness in the challenging conditions of underwater environments. The model's ability to effectively identify and classify various types of debris positions it as a leading solution for addressing the pressing issue of marine pollution.

Broader Implications

The implementation of real-time underwater garbage detection systems utilizing YOLOv8 has significant implications for environmental conservation efforts. By facilitating automated monitoring of aquatic ecosystems, these systems can contribute to more efficient waste management strategies in oceans, rivers, and lakes. Early detection of underwater debris not only aids in the timely removal of pollutants but also supports initiatives aimed at preserving marine biodiversity and enhancing ecosystem health. Furthermore, the integration of such technologies into larger automated waste management systems can enable more sustainable practices, reducing human intervention and promoting proactive measures to prevent marine pollution. Ultimately, advancements in underwater object detection like those achieved with YOLOv8 represent a crucial step toward a cleaner and healthier aquatic environment, fostering a greater awareness of and response to the environmental challenges faced by our oceans and waterways.

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